

State Research Programme "Vectors of societal cohesion" (VPP-KM-SPASA-2023/10002)

Version 1

Description

The aim of the SRP project is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of Latvia's cohesion policy since 1991, in an interdisciplinary way combining philosophical reflections on basic concepts, sociological analysis and data, legal, geographical, economic, social, cultural, ideological and other aspects. This DMP will be used to store survey data and bibliography used to convey the project. DMP is made within State Research Programme "Development of a cohesive and civically active society" project "Vectors of societal cohesion: from cohesion around the nation-state (2012-2018) to a cohesive civic community for the security of the state, society and individuals (2024-2025)" (VPP-KM-SPASA-2023/1-0002).

Funder

Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Latvia

Grant

Vectors of Societal Cohesion: from cohesion around the nation-state (2012 2018) to a cohesive civic community for the security of the state, society and individuals (2024-2025)

Researchers

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(orcid:0000-0003-0708-1977)

Organizations

Univeristy of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: State Research Programme "Vectors of societal cohesion" (VPP-KM-SPASA-2023/1 0002)

Description:

The aim of the SRP project is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of Latvia's cohesion policy since 1991, in an interdisciplinary way combining philosophical reflections on basic concepts, sociological analysis and data, legal, geographical, economic, social, cultural, ideological and other aspects. This DMP will be used to store survey data and bibliography used to convey the project. DMP is made within State Research Programme "Development of a cohesive and civically active society" project "Vectors of societal cohesion: from cohesion around the nation-state (2012-2018) to a cohesive civic community for the security of the state, society and individuals (2024-2025)" (VPP-KM-SPASA-2023/1-0002).

Researchers:

Māris Kūlis (orcid:0000-0002-6253-9023)

Kitija Mirončuka (orcid:0000-0003-0708-1977)

Organizations:

Univeristy of Latvia

Contact: Kitija Mirončuka

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Latvia

Grants: Vectors of Societal Cohesion: from cohesion around the nation-state (2012-2018) to a cohesive civic community for the security of the state, society and individuals (2024-2025)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-02-03

4. Templates

Descriptions

Sociological survey

Data fields will include personal information (age, nationality), demographic data, opinions on topics such as civic activity, social engagement, state policy, language, and media use.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The collection of survey data is intended to enhance theoretical research by providing practical insights into the views of different demographic groups on perspectives on meaning of national identity, sense of belonging, civic togetherness, as well as their experiences and views on social and geographical mobility and mutual trust.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

xls

1.1.4 Expected size of the data - give expected size and choose unit of measurement

20

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

N/A

id: null, Type: null

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Latvian policymakers, social cohesion and inclusion researchers, as well as comparative data researchers.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

If metadata is deemed important for creating a social profile (e.g. language used for survey, time taken to complete), it will be provided.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The plan is to provide the survey data only after 3 years of project implementation. This will ensure that project members have sufficient time to

finalize the research. However, possible collaborations will be reviewed, and the person in charge will be the project lead, Maris Kulis. He will review the usage and distribution of the data if there is a need to share it during the project.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The plan is to provide the survey data only after 3 years of project implementation.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Project website <https://vppsaliedetiba.lu.lv/en/>

<https://vppsaliedetiba.lu.lv/en/>

A survey data repository will be defined after the survey is finalized and the interviews are conducted. The data will be accessible via the project website and other repositories deemed fit.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

XLSM can be opened via different softwares if necessary

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

This licence lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon the data, as long as they credit the project and the original data source.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

The aim is to distribute files and data to researchers and policy makers

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2031-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

A researcher will be allocated to manage data plan.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Kitija Mirončuka (orcid:0000-0003-0708-1977)

The individual or group assigned to this task will have three main responsibilities. First, they will oversee the management and use of the data received. Second, they will handle any unforeseen requirements related to the data that are not covered in the Data Management Plan. And finally, they will work with other researchers to determine the specific purposes and methods of processing individual data.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Physical access control

Maris Kulis will see who can access data.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

One primary ethical concern revolves around privacy and consent. Participants must be fully informed about the data being collected, how it will be used, and any potential risks involved. Additionally, ensuring that the data collected is anonymized and securely stored is crucial to protect individuals' identities and prevent unauthorized access.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Conference presentations and abstracts

The "Conference presentations and abstracts" section pertains to the dissemination of research findings and insights at academic or professional conferences, summarising pre-publication presentations. These presentations and abstracts are used to share research findings with a broader audience, including peers, stakeholders, and the academic community, promoting scholarly discourse and collaboration. The primary objective is to ensure that all relevant data and findings are presented clearly and made available for further discussion and validation by the community. However, the authors reserve the right to alter or change the content of the presentations.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This data collection records conference presentations and abstracts of project participants, promoting knowledge sharing and supporting future referencing, collaboration, and knowledge exchange. It also enables the project to monitor the impact and reach of its research results within the academic community.

This data helps validate and share insights on how cohesion and civic engagement can be effectively studied, measured, and promoted. It aligns with the project's goal of advancing knowledge and developing practical strategies in these areas. By documenting and disseminating research findings presented at conferences, the project contributes to a broader conversation on these topics within academic and professional communities.

The data (conference presentations and abstracts) originates from a combination of primary sources (e.g., experiments, surveys, interviews) and secondary sources (e.g., existing datasets, literature review findings) collected throughout the research process.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

pdf

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

Yes

1.1.7 If Yes, please indicate what data set are you re-using?

Zenodo

id: <https://zenodo.org/communities/srp-vectorsofsocietalcohesion>, Type: url

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data (conference presentations and abstracts) can be valuable for researchers, policymakers, community organizers, educators, and practitioners in sociology, political science, urban studies, and public policy. Researchers can use this information to build upon existing findings. Policymakers and community organizers may leverage the insights to develop strategies that promote social cohesion and civic engagement. Additionally, educators and students can find this data useful for understanding the real-world applications of civic activity theories.

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

The data consists of conference presentations and abstracts, primarily designed for quick sharing within conference settings. These contexts provide essential details, such as summaries, author information, and conference specifics. Each

presentation and abstract is self-contained, making additional metadata unnecessary. Since these formats are typically intended for brief communication rather than deep analysis or reuse, formal metadata is unlikely to significantly enhance their usability or value.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

The data generated, specifically conference presentations and abstracts, will have restricted access. Access will be limited to project collaborators and authorized stakeholders to protect any sensitive information or preliminary findings that may not be ready for full public release. Yet most of the data will be open access.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/srp-vectorsofsocietalcohesion>

Repositories typically prioritize final, peer-reviewed publications, but this repository will allow us to store and share preliminary materials, such as conference presentations, that are not yet finalized.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Word, Adobe, Foxit, Web

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The CC BY 4.0 license provides a flexible yet open framework that allows others to freely access, use, and build upon the research, provided they credit the original authors. By choosing this license, we maximize the impact and reach of our work, supporting transparency and collaboration in research on cohesion and civic activity.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

Yes, the data generated during the project will be usable by third parties even after the project concludes. By employing the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license, we ensure that the data, including conference presentations and abstracts, can be accessed, utilized, and built upon by researchers, policymakers, and practitioners in the field.

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2024-10-30

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2028-10-10

The data generated during the project will be available for a minimum of four years or as long as necessary, ensuring continued access to preliminary findings and insights. Although the project is scheduled to conclude in one year, we are dedicated to making the data publicly accessible.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

Digital access will be further protected by strong passwords, ensuring that only authorized users can view or manipulate the data.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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